

Tokenization Trade-offs in Neural Abstractive Summarization: A Controlled Study of Efficiency, Coverage, and Performance

Byshin Semen*

Baikal School of BRICS

Irkutsk National Research Technical University (INRTU)

Irkutsk, Russia

bishinsemyon@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0007-1019-1751

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Abstract

Tokenization is a fundamental yet often underexamined component of modern natural language processing pipelines, directly influencing model efficiency, capacity, and output quality. In this work, we present a controlled empirical study of tokenization strategies for abstractive summarization using a $\sim 200\text{M}$ -parameter encoder-decoder transformer architecture. We compare word-level, Byte Pair Encoding (BPE), Unigram language modeling, and character-level tokenization under identical training conditions, and further evaluate a hybrid character-level approach based on Gradient-Based Subword Tokenization (GBST) from Charformer.

Our analysis focuses on the trade-offs between vocabulary size, sequence length, out-of-vocabulary (OOV) rates, and computational efficiency. We show that while character-level tokenization eliminates OOV issues, it incurs substantial computational overhead due to sequence length inflation. Word-level tokenization, despite its efficiency, suffers from high OOV rates under fixed vocabulary constraints. Subword approaches such as BPE and Unigram provide a balanced compromise between coverage and efficiency, while GBST offers an effective hybrid solution that reduces sequence length while preserving character-level granularity.

All models are trained under a compute-optimal regime following Chinchilla scaling principles, ensuring a fair comparison across tokenization schemes. We release our code and trained models to facilitate reproducibility and further research on tokenization design.

1 Introduction

Tokenization is a fundamental component of data preparation in modern natural language processing pipelines, directly influencing how a model represents input text and generates output sequences. Despite this, it is often treated as a secondary design choice compared to model architecture. However, the choice of tokenization scheme affects not only model effectiveness and computational efficiency, but also model capacity, as vocabulary size contributes directly to the number of trainable parameters.

Modern NLP pipelines have largely standardized the use of subword tokenization methods, particularly Byte Pair Encoding (BPE) and Unigram language modeling, across a wide range of tasks. These approaches offer a practical trade-off between vocabulary size and coverage, achieving robustness to rare words while avoiding the excessive sequence lengths typical of character-level tokenization.

However, this trend often overlooks alternative regimes. Word-level tokenization, while sensitive to vocabulary size, can remain competitive in certain settings; for example, (Hu 2025) show that it performs strongly for agglutinative languages such as Turkish and Finnish. At the other extreme, character-level tokenization provides maximal granularity and eliminates out-of-vocabulary issues, albeit at a significant computational cost.

Motivated by these trade-offs, we conduct a controlled study of tokenization strategies for abstractive summarization using a $\sim 200\text{M}$ -parameter transformer architecture. We compare character-level, word-level, BPE, and Unigram tokenization schemes under identical model architectures and training budgets. In addition, we incorporate Charformer (Tay et al. 2022), which introduces Gradient-Based Subword Tokenization (GBST) to down-sample character-level inputs, enabling subword-level ef-

*Supervisor: Nazih Errahel

efficiency while retaining character-level decoding.

Our contributions are as follows:

- A controlled comparison of multiple tokenization regimes under near-identical model architectures and compute budgets.
- An analysis of the trade-offs between sequence length, OOV rates, and computational efficiency across tokenization methods.
- An empirical evaluation of hybrid character-level tokenization with GBST in the context of abstractive summarization.
- Public release of trained models and code to support reproducibility.¹

2 Data preparation

2.1 Dataset

We use the CNN/DailyMail (CNN/DM) summarization dataset (See et al. 2017), obtained from the Kaggle repository². The non-anonymized version is used to preserve named entities, which is important for evaluating tokenizer performance on out-of-vocabulary (OOV) words. The dataset consists of 311,971 samples, split into 287,113 for training, 13,368 for validation, and 11,490 for testing. However, some of the samples can be considered outliers and some are misparsed due to irregular article/summary formatting.

We assume that the provided training, validation, and test splits are representative subsets of the full dataset, such that the validation and test sets do not differ substantially in distribution from the training set. This assumption allows us to treat the splits as roughly comparable for model evaluation and analysis.

In this configuration, the news article serves as the input sequence, while the associated highlights serve as the target summary. The dataset presents a significant memory challenge due to the variable length of input articles, with a mean pre-cleaning length of 4,033 characters (Table 1). This length distribution directly drives the peak GPU memory consumption during attention computation.

2.2 Text Cleaning

To ensure data quality and stable training, we remove all markers and non-english text. The article-to-summary length ratios in Table 1 range from 0.003 to 18.333, indicating the presence of misparsed or irregular samples. The cleaning procedure includes:

¹<https://github.com/SentrixGD/Tokenization-Effects-on-Machine-Summarization>, accessed April 2026

²<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/gowrishankarp/newspaper-text-summarization-cnn-dailymail>, accessed February 2026

- Removing author bylines (e.g., "By Author Name") and CNN-specific markers such as "(CNN) —".
- Deleting "PUBLISHED:" lines, updated metadata, and other headers.
- Applying ASCII folding and removing remaining non-English or special characters.
- Normalizing whitespace by collapsing multiple spaces and newlines into single spaces.
- Fixing common punctuation issues, such as spacing around punctuation and multiple periods. In order to avoid artifacts like words combined with punctuation, we surround all non-letter and non-digit symbols by single whitespaces.
- Standardizing quotes and apostrophes by converting curly quotes to straight quotes.

The effect of this cleaning is relatively small in terms of text length but significant for data quality. Across the training set, approximately 801 million raw characters were processed, with 9.46 million characters (1.18%) removed. Specific patterns removed include double hyphens (195,584 occurrences), CNN markers (57,411), "PUBLISHED" lines (42,274), and curly quotes (1,048,450). ASCII folding removed an additional 2.02 million characters (0.25%). After cleaning, the dataset contains 95 unique characters, with the top 20 characters dominated by standard letters and whitespace.

This preprocessing ensures that subsequent length-based filtering and model training operate on clean, standardized text, improving the reliability and reproducibility of downstream analysis and summarization experiments.

2.3 Filtering Misparsed Samples

To ensure data quality and stable training, we remove extreme outliers based on article and summary lengths. The article-to-summary length ratios in Table 1 range from 0.003 to 18.333, indicating the presence of misparsed or irregular samples.

We apply three filtering rules:

- Articles must contain at least 250 symbols.
- The article-to-summary length ratio must be at least 0.05.
- The article-to-summary length ratio must not exceed 0.5.

Applying these criteria eliminates abnormally short or unbalanced samples. The cleaning decreases the mean article length by 13.9%, the 25th percentile by 9.9%, the median by 12%, and the 75th percentile by 15.2%, while

Statistic	mean	std	min	25 %	50 %	75 %	max
Words	374.099	385.538	9	56	151	642	2238
Candidates	74.211	77.901	0	11	29	127	523
Replaced	43.868	45.512	0	6	18	75	262
Replaced ratio	0.143	0.01	0	0.14	0.148	0.149	0.15
Replaced adjectives	10.719	11.817	0	1	5	18	105
Replaced adverbs	6.236	7.663	0	0	2	10	69
Replaced verbs	26.913	27.919	0	4	12	46	188
Semantic similarity	0.995	0.004	0.927	0.993	0.996	0.998	1

Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the augmentation process at the sequence level with the total of 456334 samples. “Words” denotes the number of valid tokens per sequence after filtering, while “Candidates” refers to tokens eligible for augmentation (verbs, adjectives, and adverbs). “Replaced” indicates the number of tokens actually substituted, with “Replaced ratio” showing the proportion of replacements relative to valid tokens. Replacement counts are further broken down by part of speech. “Semantic similarity” measures the similarity between original and augmented sequences, indicating minimal semantic drift.

Statistic	count	mean	std	50 %	90 %	90%	Threshold	Inflation ratio
Word-level	426 564	576.482	225.643	558	899	1009	1109	1.03
BPE	427 435	698.727	268.366	679	1083	1205	1325	1.249
Unigram	427 460	769.441	297.264	747	1195	1330	1463	1.374
Char-level	427 655	3280.792	1255.332	3187	5081	5639	6202	5.865

Table 3: Post-tokenization article length statistics. The “count” column reports the number of samples after cleaning. The bold column indicates the 90th percentile before cleaning, while the non-bold column shows the 90th percentile after cleaning. The “threshold” column sets the maximum sequence length (90th percentile \times 1.1) to prevent severe truncation, and the “compression ratio” indicates the reduction in average length relative to the original word-level sequences.

Figure 3: Part-of-speech (POS) distribution before and after augmentation. The distributional changes reflect the selective modification of specific POS categories while preserving the broader syntactic structure of the corpus, slightly shifting the overall part of speech distribution among all words.

3 Tokenization

3.1 Overview

To study the impact of tokenization on model behavior, we train five models with identical architecture and approximately 200M parameters, differing only in their tokenization schemes. The evaluated approaches include SentencePiece-based word-level tokenization, Byte Pair Encoding (BPE), Unigram language modeling, and character-level tokenization. In addition, we consider a hybrid variant that augments the character-level model with a Gradient-Based Subword Tokenization (GBST) module following (Tay et al. 2022).

We analyze how these tokenization regimes affect training dynamics, inference efficiency, and the qualitative properties of the generated outputs.

3.2 Post-tokenization Cleaning

Initial cleaning alone is insufficient for autoregressive summarization. To balance coverage and efficiency, we examine the length distributions of tokenized corpora (Table 3). The threshold is set to 110% of the 90th percentile to avoid truncating more than 10% of the se-

quence, ensuring the model retains sufficient context during training.

3.3 Word-level tokenization

Word-level tokenization is the simplest regime considered, splitting sequences into tokens by whitespace. For all non-character-level methods, the vocabulary size is fixed at 32,000. Due to the content of CNN/DM, which contains many low-frequency words, word-level tokenization suffers from a high number of out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens. (**webster-kit-1992-tokenization**) identifies splitting text into words as an essential step in natural language processing. (Hu 2025) report experiments on 10,000 Wikipedia articles and find that word-level tokenization achieves the highest F1 score; however, they use the entire set of unique words for the word-level regime while limiting vocabulary sizes for the other methods. In contrast, our approach applies the same vocabulary size limit to all non-character-level tokenizations, resulting in word-level sequences with significant OOV noise, accounting for 8.87% of tokens in the training set.

3.4 Byte-Pair-Encoding

Byte Pair Encoding (BPE) is a subword tokenization method that iteratively merges the most frequent pairs of symbols to construct a fixed-size vocabulary (Sennrich et al. 2016). Starting from a character-level representation, BPE learns a set of merge operations that capture frequent subword patterns, allowing it to represent both common words as single tokens and rare words as compositions of subword units. In contrast to word-level tokenization, BPE significantly reduces the number of out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens while maintaining a manageable vocabulary size. However, this comes at the cost of increased sequence length, as words may be split into multiple subword tokens. In our setup, the vocabulary size is fixed at 32,000, enforcing a trade-off between vocabulary coverage and sequence length. This enables more robust handling of rare and morphologically complex words compared to the word-level regime, while introducing additional computational overhead during training and inference. Nevertheless, the computational overhead remains modest: as shown in Table 3, the average length ratio is 1.249, while out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens account for less than 0.01% (38 out of 327 535 918) of all tokens in the training corpus.

3.5 Unigram tokenization

(Kudo 2018) introduces a probabilistic approach to subword tokenization. While similar to BPE in producing subword units, Unigram models tokenization as a likelihood-based segmentation problem, selecting subword sequences that maximize the probability of the cor-

pus rather than applying deterministic merge operations. As a result, multiple valid segmentations may exist for a given sequence, which can introduce variability in tokenization. Despite this difference, Unigram remains a competitive tokenization strategy and is included in this study to assess its impact on data representation and model performance. As shown in Table 3, Unigram produces longer sequences than BPE, with an average length ratio of 1.374 compared to 1.249, reflecting a different trade-off between vocabulary compactness and sequence length. Due to the higher computational cost of training the Unigram tokenizer, we restrict training to a subset of 150 000 samples. Under this constraint, the resulting tokenization exhibits a higher proportion of out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens, accounting for 1.83% (660 511 out of 360 357 112) of all tokens in the training corpus.

3.6 Character-level tokenization

Character-level tokenization represents text as sequences of individual characters, resulting in a minimal and fixed vocabulary while effectively eliminating out-of-vocabulary (OOV) issues (Kim et al. 2015). This approach provides full coverage of the input space and is particularly robust to rare words and morphological variation. However, these advantages come at the cost of substantially increased sequence length. As shown in Table 3, character-level tokenization produces sequences that are on average 5.865 times longer than their whitespace-tokenized counterparts, leading to significantly higher computational overhead (approximately 7–9× compared to BPE in our setup). This increase directly impacts training and inference efficiency due to the quadratic complexity of attention mechanisms. Despite this, character-level tokenization yields the lowest proportion of OOV tokens among all evaluated methods (38 out of 1,533,805,171 tokens), effectively eliminating vocabulary coverage issues. Consequently, it highlights a fundamental trade-off between coverage and computational efficiency, contrasting sharply with subword-based approaches.

4 Model Architecture

Encoder-Decoder Setup: We implement five transformer-based encoder-decoder models (Vaswani et al. 2017), each with approximately 200M parameters. All architectures are identical except for the Charformer variant (Tay et al. 2022), and they differ only in their tokenization schemes. The encoder enables the model to build a structured internal representation of the input article, effectively “understanding” its content before generating a summary. This explicit separation of encoding and decoding improves the handling of long-range dependencies and variable-length inputs. Consequently, we adopt an encoder-decoder architecture rather than a

decoder-only setup. (Fu et al. 2023) empirically supports this choice, showing that encoder-decoder models outperform decoder-only variants on sequence-to-sequence tasks, as decoder-only models are prone to attention degeneration when input and target lengths differ significantly.

Attention Mechanism: We employ FlashAttention-2 (Dao 2023) to reduce memory usage and accelerate training on long sequences. All models are implemented using the PyTorch built-in FlashAttention-2 kernel and trained on the Ada-Lovelace GPU architecture, which provides optimal support for this version.

Positional Encodings: Rotary Positional Embeddings (RoPE) (Su et al. 2023) provide continuous and extrapolatable position information, improving the model’s handling of long inputs. Unlike other positional embedding methods (**press-et al-2022-alibi**; **peng-et al-2026-yarn**; Vaswani et al. 2017), RoPE encodes absolute positions while implicitly implementing relative positional information through the differences in rotation angles. This approach does not add any trainable parameters and is computationally efficient, as the angles can be precomputed and stored rather than recomputed in every iteration.

Feedforward Layer: Our model employs a three-layer GLU variant, similar in design to the SwiGLU used in LLaMA and PaLM (Shazeer 2020; Touvron et al. 2023; Chowdhery et al. 2022). The module consists of a gate projection, an up projection, and a down projection to map back to the embedding dimension, using SiLU as the nonlinearity. This structure increases expressivity while retaining the gating benefits of traditional GLUs. Following LLaMA, we retain an optimal weight balance by reducing the number of parameters per GLU layer to $\frac{2}{3} \cdot 4d$, reflecting the use of three layers instead of two in the MLP feedforward block.

Normalization and Depth Scaling: We apply the LayerNorm scaling method from (Sun et al. 2026) to stabilize training in deep networks, mitigating the so-called curse of depth. This technique regulates both forward activations and gradients, enabling stable training even with 16-bit floating-point precision.

GBST: We incorporate the Gradient-Based Subword Tokenization (GBST) module from Charformer (Tay et al. 2022) while retaining the chosen tokenization regime. Specifically, we apply character-level tokenization and use GBST to downsample the input via a learned subnetwork that weights merges up to a target downsampling size. This approach bridges character-level granularity with subword-level efficiency, which is particularly beneficial for summarization tasks where the decoding sequence is much shorter. Empirically, it has minimal impact on effectiveness compared to a fully character-level encoding.

5 Training Setup

Model size: All models use 12 encoder and 12 decoder transformer layers, with 8 attention heads and a 768-dimensional embedding (also used as hidden dimension) and 0.1 dropout throughout the model, totaling approximately 198M parameters. BPE, Unicode, and Word-level tokenization models have slightly larger sizes (223M) due to expanded vocabulary and output layers.

Optimizer: We train all models using Adam (Kingma and Ba 2017) with $\beta_1 = 0.9$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$.

Training length: All models are trained according to the Chinchilla scaling law (Hoffmann et al. 2022). Instead of recalculating from the formulas, we adopt an approximate heuristic of 20 tokens per trainable parameter, which we consider compute-optimal for our setup (3.97B tokens for 198M-parameter models and 4.46B tokens for 223M-parameter models). We use a batch size of 32 with gradient accumulation to reduce memory overhead. The number of epochs depends on the corpus size and the number of optimal tokens, ranging from 2.45 to 16.54 iterations. (Raffel et al. 2023) empirically shows that such iteration counts do not significantly harm performance and may even outperform in scenarios with minimal data repetition.

Progress monitoring: Each model saves an intermediate checkpoint every 1 000 optimization steps. Due to the size of the validation set and the frequency of evaluation, full validation becomes computationally expensive. Instead, we monitor progress by autoregressively decoding a representative sample using both greedy and multinomial decoding.

Learning rate scheduling: We use a learning rate schedule with 4,000 linear warmup steps, peaking at 1×10^{-4} , followed by linear decay to the end of training. The warmup phase stabilizes early optimization, while the subsequent decay allows the model to effectively explore the optimization landscape and gradually converge to a well-performing minimum.

6 Results

6.1 Byte-Pair Encoding

Byte Pair Encoding (BPE) achieves consistently strong performance across all evaluation metrics according to the Table 4. It attains high ROUGE scores, indicating effective n-gram overlap with reference summaries and solid preservation of both lexical content and structural patterns. In particular, the ROUGE-1 and ROUGE-L values suggest that BPE captures salient information and maintains coherent phrasing.

This behavior is further supported by BERTScore, where BPE achieves one of the highest values, reflecting strong semantic similarity between generated and reference summaries. Compared to Unigram, BPE

Statistic	ROUGE-1	ROUGE-2	ROUGE-L	METEOR	BERT-P	BERT-R	BERT-F1	time
BPE	0.343	0.120	0.225	0.262	0.175	0.178	0.177	2.582
Word	0.238	0.036	0.151	0.197	0.076	0.055	0.067	1.347
Unigram	0.354	0.127	0.233	0.243	0.188	0.161	0.175	2.530
Char-level	0.096	0.004	0.069	0.080	-0.564	-0.174	-0.376	66.294
Charformer	0.208	0.021	0.129	0.137	-0.082	-0.104	-0.092	14.328

Table 4: Results of the evaluation of each regime. All evaluations are conducted on the same test subset of 1024 samples. BERT-P stands for the Precision metric, BERT-R stands for the Recall metric. Time column represents the average speed of inference of one sample in seconds. BERTScore is computed with baseline rescaling, following the standard implementation. As a result, scores are centered and may take negative values, reflecting relative similarity with respect to a pretrained baseline. Best results are highlighted in bold.

yields slightly lower ROUGE scores but comparable BERTScore, suggesting a similar level of semantic fidelity despite differences in segmentation strategy.

In terms of efficiency, BPE remains competitive. Although it produces longer sequences than word-level tokenization, its inference time is only moderately higher, demonstrating a favorable trade-off between computational cost and summary quality.

6.2 Word-Level Tokenization

Word-level tokenization underperforms relative to subword approaches across all evaluation metrics. Lower ROUGE scores indicate reduced n-gram overlap and weaker preservation of both lexical and structural information, while the substantially lower BERTScore reflects diminished semantic alignment with reference summaries.

A key contributing factor is the high proportion of out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens, which account for 8.87% of the training data due to the imposed vocabulary limit of 32 000. This restriction significantly limits the model’s ability to represent rare words and morphological variations, leading to information loss and degraded summary quality.

Despite these limitations, word-level tokenization is the most efficient regime in terms of inference time, requiring approximately half the decoding time of BPE. This highlights a clear trade-off between computational efficiency and representational capacity.

6.3 Unigram Tokenization

Unigram tokenization achieves performance comparable to BPE and attains the highest ROUGE scores among all evaluated regimes. In particular, it slightly outperforms BPE on ROUGE-1, ROUGE-2, and ROUGE-L, indicating improved n-gram overlap and structural alignment with reference summaries. Notably, this is achieved despite a higher proportion of out-of-vocabulary (OOV) tokens (1.83% of all tokens in the training corpus), mak-

ing the results particularly competitive under the same vocabulary constraints.

However, this advantage does not consistently translate to semantic similarity. While BERTScore precision is the highest among all models, recall is lower than that of BPE, resulting in a slightly reduced F1 score. This suggests that Unigram tokenization may favor locally accurate token choices without fully capturing the global semantic content of the reference summaries.

In terms of efficiency, Unigram exhibits inference time comparable to BPE. However, training the Unigram tokenizer itself is more computationally demanding due to its probabilistic formulation, which requires estimating a distribution over possible segmentations, in contrast to the deterministic merge operations used in BPE.

Overall, these results indicate that Unigram provides a competitive alternative to BPE, with a slightly different trade-off between lexical overlap, semantic consistency, and preprocessing cost.

6.4 Character-Level Tokenization

Character-level tokenization yields the lowest performance across all evaluation metrics. ROUGE scores are substantially lower than those of subword-based methods, indicating limited n-gram overlap and weak structural alignment with reference summaries.

This trend is further reflected in BERTScore, where all metrics are strongly negative, indicating poor semantic similarity relative to the baseline. Despite eliminating out-of-vocabulary issues, character-level representations struggle to capture higher-level linguistic structure in abstractive summarization tasks.

A key factor contributing to this behavior is the decoding process. Since the model operates entirely at the character level, it must generate coherent words and phrases without explicit subword or word-level constraints. In practice, this leads to frequent spelling inconsistencies and, more importantly, severe hallucinations, where generated content diverges from the source article. These effects are reflected in the extremely low

BERTScore values.

In addition to reduced effectiveness, character-level tokenization incurs a substantial computational cost. The average inference time is more than an order of magnitude higher than that of subword methods, directly resulting from the significantly longer input sequences. This highlights a clear trade-off, where the benefits of full coverage are outweighed by both reduced performance and increased computational demands in this setting.

6.5 Charformer

Charformer improves upon pure character-level tokenization but remains substantially behind subword-based approaches. ROUGE scores indicate moderate gains over the character-level baseline, suggesting that the GBST module partially recovers meaningful subword structure from character inputs.

However, overall performance remains below that of both BPE and Unigram. BERTScore values, while higher than those of the character-level model, remain negative, indicating that semantic alignment with reference summaries is still limited. This suggests that, although GBST mitigates some of the issues associated with character-level representations, it does not fully resolve them.

Similar to the character-level model, Charformer decodes sequences at the character level. While the GBST module downscales the input during encoding—effectively approximating subword representations—this does not fully constrain the decoding process. As a result, the model still exhibits spelling inconsistencies and hallucination effects, albeit to a lesser extent than the pure character-level approach. The impact of these issues is reflected in the comparatively low BERTScore values.

From an efficiency perspective, Charformer significantly reduces the computational overhead compared to character-level tokenization, but inference time remains notably higher than subword methods. This effect is further amplified by the nature of the summarization task. While the decoder generates relatively short sequences (on average 10.1% (Table 1) of the input length), the encoder must process the full-length input, where GBST operates to downsample character-level representations. As a result, the computational cost is dominated by encoding long sequences, and the benefits of shorter output decoding are insufficient to offset this overhead. This highlights that, although GBST improves the efficiency-quality trade-off, it does not fully bridge the gap with standard subword tokenization in encoder-decoder summarization settings.

7 Conclusion

Tokenization plays a crucial role in natural language processing pipelines, directly influencing model effectiveness, efficiency, and capacity, yet it is often treated as a secondary design choice. In this work, we conducted a controlled study comparing character-level, word-level, BPE, Unigram, and GBST (Charformer) tokenization strategies on a ~ 200 M-parameter transformer architecture for abstractive summarization.

Our analysis highlights the trade-offs inherent in different tokenization regimes. Character-level tokenization achieves minimal out-of-vocabulary issues but incurs significant computational overhead and hallucinations, while word-level approach in spite of its efficiency suffers from OOV tokens to the point that it hurts the performance compared to the subword regimes. Subword tokenization methods, such as BPE and Unigram, provide a balanced trade-off between efficiency and coverage. Finally, hybrid approaches like GBST offer a promising compromise, maintaining character-level granularity while reducing sequence length and computational cost.

These results emphasize the importance of carefully selecting a tokenization strategy based on task requirements, data characteristics, and hardware constraints. We release all trained models and code to support reproducibility and further research.³

8 Limitations

This study is restricted to English abstractive summarization using the CNN/DailyMail dataset. As a result, the findings may not fully generalize to multilingual settings, where tokenization plays a more critical role due to increased lexical diversity and script variation. Extending this analysis to multilingual corpora is a natural direction for future work and would likely amplify the advantages of tokenization regimes with small or fixed vocabularies, such as character-level tokenization and Charformer.

In such settings, it would also be valuable to include byte-level and hash-based approaches, such as CANINE (Clark et al. 2022) and ByT5 (Xue et al. 2022), which are specifically designed to operate without a predefined subword vocabulary. These methods offer improved scalability across languages but do not provide clear advantages over character-level tokenization in a strictly monolingual setup, which motivated their exclusion from the present study.

Another limitation concerns model scale. All experiments are conducted on ~ 200 M-parameter models with fixed architectural configurations. While this enables controlled comparison, it does not capture how tokenization strategies interact with model scaling. Fu-

³<https://github.com/SentrixGD/Tokenization-Effects-on-Machine-Summarization>, accessed April 2026

ture work could explore a broader range of model sizes, varying both transformer depth and vocabulary-dependent components, to better understand how tokenization influences representational capacity, parameter allocation, and convergence behavior under different scaling regimes.

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